

Composition of graminaceous and cyperaceous weed flora during a 2-year period at the plant virus experimental field, Kalyani, West Bengal, India.

Weed	Av no./m ²		Relative occurrence (%)	
	1976-77	1977-78	1976-77	1977-78
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i> (Graminae)	182	300	53.8	43.8
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> (Cyperaceae)	55	174	16.2	25.4
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (Graminae)	71	122	21.1	17.8
<i>Paspalum notavum</i> (Graminae)	30	58	8.8	8.5

kharif. The pots were used as virus sources in the field 35 to 40 days after inoculation. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of TN1, Jaya, and Ratna were transplanted in replicated 1-m² plots prepared in random block design. One pot of inoculated *E. colonum* was placed

at the center of each plot. Each plot was then covered with nylon netting on wooden frames. Freshly emerged leafhoppers were released into each covered plot. The plants in each plot were observed until the booting stage. Ratna plants had 1.57% infection; Jaya,

6.4%; and TN1, 7.5%.

From this experiment it is apparent that the predominant graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds at the Kalyani virus experimental field do not contain any virus in natural conditions.

Weeds collected at Kalyani and other locations were inoculated with the virus. Only *E. colonum* and *P. notavum* were able to maintain the virus for 3 months.

In the field study with the inoculated *E. colonum* as the source plant, the virus was transmitted to all three test varieties (Ratna, Jaya, and TN1). Thus it is apparent that infected weeds such as *E. colonum* can act as the tungro virus source in the field. But no virus was detected in the weeds in natural conditions. Therefore, weeds may not play an important role in the field transmission of tungro. □

Occurrence of *Phaeotrichoconis crotalariae* on rice in Karnataka, India

S. Kumaraswamy, assistant plant protection specialist (pathology) University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya, Karnataka, India

Many prerelease and released paddy cultures suffered from grain discoloration in 1977 kharif and 1978 summer in experimental plots at the Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya, Karnataka. Derivatives of Basumathi and Sabarmati were particularly affected. When the discolored kernels were surface sterilized and incubated in moist chambers at room temperature (25-27°C), abundant spores of *Phaeotrichoconis crotalariae*, as well as the commonly known fungi involved in discoloration, were encountered. The fungus was easily isolated by the single-spore technique and pure-cultured on potato-dextrose agar. In the initial stages, the mycelial growth was whitish, but at maturity became dark grey. Conidia were produced after 4 days; sclerotia developed after 8 to 10 days. Descriptions of the fungus are similar to those provided by Subramanyam in 1956 and Vaidehi in 1971. Vaidehi had

isolated this fungus from TN1 rice kernels collected in 1967 in Andhra Pradesh, but the same fungus now occurs regularly and abundantly on many rice

varieties in Karnataka. This is the only information reported on its widespread occurrence on different rice varieties in Karnataka.

A rice disease observed by the late Bill Golden in Nepal

K. C. Ling, plant pathologist, International Rice Research Institute

After reading the article "Symptoms resembling those of rice dwarf disease in the Kathmandu Valley, Nepal" in the

IRRN 3(6):13-14, 1978, I found a color slide that was given to me by the late William (Bill) G. Golden, Jr., former IRRI rice production specialist and formerly with IRRI outreach programs in Sri Lanka and Bangladesh. The slide, taken by Bill in Kathmandu, Nepal, on 3 October 1966, shows A. N. Bhattarai

A photograph from a color slide taken by the late William G. Golden, Jr., in Kathmandu, Nepal, in 1966 showing A. N. Bhattarai holding a rice hill with symptoms similar to those of rice dwarf disease described in Japan.